

THE NATURE OF THE POSTGRADUATE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF THE UZBEK SSR UNDER THE SOVIET GOVERNMENT

Nasilloev Sunnat Shavkat ogli

Second-year PhD student, Bukhara State University

E-mail: s.sh.nasillayev@buxdu.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15208871>

Abstract: This article highlights the challenges and solutions in the training of scientific personnel through postgraduate education in the Uzbek SSR. The Soviet government aimed to utilize scientific achievements as a solution to existing and potential socio-economic problems. In the Soviet Union, favorable conditions were created for research in higher education, and decisions were made to improve the research system, with the goal of enhancing the scientific status of the republics and securing greater economic benefit.

Keywords: Council of Ministers, Uzbek SSR, personnel, Doctor of Science, postgraduate education, dissertation, production.

ХАРАКТЕР СИСТЕМЫ ПОСЛЕВУЗОВСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ УЗБЕКСКОЙ ССР В ГОДЫ СОВЕТСКОЙ ВЛАСТИ

Аннотация: В данной статье освещаются проблемы и пути их решения в подготовке научных кадров через аспирантуру в Узбекской ССР. Советское правительство стремилось использовать достижения науки для решения существующих и потенциальных социально-экономических проблем. В Советском Союзе были созданы благоприятные условия для научных исследований в системе высшего образования, а также приняты меры по совершенствованию научной деятельности с целью повышения научного статуса союзных республик и получения большей экономической выгоды.

Ключевые слова: Совет Министров, Узбекская ССР, кадры, доктор наук, аспирантура, диссертация, производство.

INTRODUCTION

During the peak of World War II, all sectors of the national economy were redirected to meet the needs of the front. In order to improve the scope and quality of research, measures were taken to enhance the postgraduate system that allowed for research activities independent of production. However, in the years 1941–1942, the planned admissions to postgraduate programs were not satisfactorily fulfilled. Scientific and educational work with postgraduate students was not well organized. An inspection carried out by the All-Union Committee for Higher Education under the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR revealed that many heads of state educational institutions and directors of higher education institutions did not pay sufficient attention to working with postgraduate students. As a result, many postgraduate students, including those in their final year, were found to have severed ties with their institutions.

Another important point is that on November 16, 1967, the Central Committee of the CPSU and the Council of Ministers of the USSR issued Resolution No. 1064, and on February 13, 1968, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR issued Resolution No. 52, approving the directive "On the Improvement of the Training of Scientific and Scientific-Pedagogical Personnel."

According to the decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR, between 1960 and 1967, scientific personnel capable of addressing the major issues put forward by the practice of "communist construction" had been developed in the republic. There were also improvements in the training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel. By 1968, nearly 5,000 scientific workers in the republic held academic degrees, including over 350 Doctors of Science. More than 3,000 postgraduate students were actively engaged in research. Taking into account that many specialists were working on dissertations independently, outside of the formal postgraduate system, this number is likely even higher.

Object and Methods of Research: Valuable archival documents were examined using comparative-historical, critical, and objective analysis methods.

RESULTS

To address existing issues, the All-Union Committee for Higher Education under the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR issued directive No. D-09-45¹ on December 18, 1942, "On the Registration of Postgraduate Students," instructing universities to establish proper registration procedures, reconnect with students who had left during wartime, return successful students, and provide favorable conditions for research and dissertation work. Directors, department heads, and academic supervisors were required to monitor students' progress and report research plans to the Committee.

On July 14, 1943, the Committee issued order No. 189², approving the admission plan for postgraduate studies in higher education institutions across the USSR for 1,352 candidates, with a separate list of 250 students to receive military deferments. Enterprises and institutions were instructed to grant applicants 15 days of unpaid leave for entrance exams.

The order signed by Deputy Chairman V. Molotov and Secretary M. Smirnyukov stipulated that admitted postgraduates must be released from work within a month to focus exclusively on research.

DISCUSSION

The order also covered new admission plans by field and institution, approving 832 external study positions and encouraging university directors to include assistants and instructors without degrees but with research potential. It required the return of postgraduates who had temporarily severed ties and called for the introduction of distance learning for those unable to return due to work conditions.

However, the 1960s saw significant shortcomings in scientific training. Young specialists capable of conducting research were not adequately recruited, and many failed to complete dissertations on time. Of 748 students who graduated in 1966, only 64 defended their dissertations promptly. In the Ministry of Agriculture's institutes, only 3 out of 76 students defended on time in 1966, and only 3 out of 64 in 1967. This was due to poor candidate selection, lack of proper research and living conditions, and insufficient involvement of senior scientists and professors.

Postgraduate training plans in vital agricultural sectors were consistently unmet. Institutions often substituted specialties and failed to enroll new students for two years. For instance, in three consecutive years, no students at the Central Asian Sericulture Research Institute

¹ BVDA 532-C-fond, 1-ro'yxat, 78-yig'majild, 34-varaq.

² BVDA 532-C-fond, 1-ro'yxat, 78-yig'majild, 106-varaq.

defended dissertations. Similarly, in 1967, there were no dissertation defenses at the Rainfed Agriculture Institute.

The shortcomings in training scientific and pedagogical personnel were mainly attributed to the Ministry's Scientific Directorate, which paid little attention to this task, poorly supervised research institutions, and provided inadequate support.

CONCLUSION

These findings indicate that scientific training through postgraduate education in agricultural sciences in the Uzbek SSR was poorly organized. Due to the historical importance of legal documents on the Soviet government's science policy, researchers must thoroughly examine archival sources when studying the history of science in Uzbekistan. Literature from 1941–1945 largely reflected Soviet ideology rather than critical perspectives. Despite numerous decrees and orders issued on scientific training in the Uzbek SSR, existing problems were not effectively resolved. On October 25, 1971, a meeting of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Uzbek SSR, chaired by E. Shaykhov, approved decree No. 85 “On the Training of Scientific Personnel through Postgraduate Studies.” It proposed an annual increase of 10–12 spots in economics-related postgraduate programs to support the republic's economic development.

REFERENCES

1. S.Sh. “Nasilloev Sovet hokimiyatining O‘zbekiston SSRdagi ilm-fan siyosati” Iqtidorli talabalar, magistrantlar, tayanch doktorantlar va doktorantlarning “TAFAKKUR VA TALQIN” mavzusidagi respublika miqyosidagi ilmiy-amaliy anjuman to‘plami II qism. Buxoro – 2023. 7-12 b.
2. S.Sh. Nasilloev, “Sovet hukumatining O‘zbekiston SSR oliy yurtlarida aspirantura bosqichini tartibga solish sohasidagi huquqiy hujjatlari va ularning mohiyati. (ikkinchi jahon urushi davrida)” Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali, № 17(54). 49-55 b.
3. S.Sh.Nasilloev “O‘zbekiston fanlar akademiyasining tashkil etilishi” RESEARCH FOCUS xalqaro ilmiy jurnali 2023 yil 5-son 92-98 b.
4. Materials of the National Archives of Uzbekistan.